

ARCTIC PASSION

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Report on development of website with protocols, planning and reporting tools for the Atlantic-Arctic Distributed Biological Observatory network

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**ARCTIC
PASSION**

Work package 1

Establishing an adaptive and more complete Arctic observing system

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Coordinator accepted

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Introduction

Increased collaboration on marine observations in the European sector of the Arctic is a major focus of Arctic PASSION. Through stronger collaboration we can utilize existing resources better (reduced overlap), improve the output from ongoing and future monitoring as well as science projects - through communal priorities and standardized protocols for data collection, analysis and sharing. The organizational vehicle to make significant progress in this direction for ocean observations is the establishment of regional Distributed Biological Observatories (DBOs), which are linked in an informal pan-Arctic DBO network across the Arctic Ocean (Figure 1).

Arctic PASSION has provided the means for increased coordination capabilities to establish the Atlantic-Arctic DBO (A-DBO), with common tools for planning and reporting observational data. The work is carried out by a work group with partners both within and outside Arctic PASSION, in close interaction with the A-DBO community through recurrent meeting activities and collaborative exercises based on the periodic annual cycle of the DBO concept. As the main hub for information exchange, a web page has been set up within the Arctic PASSION project web site. This report describes the current state of development for this web page, including some thoughts on further development beyond the Arctic PASSION project lifetime.

Figure 1. The constellation of the current four regional Arctic DBOs (Pacific, Baffin Bay/Davis Strait, Siberian, and Atlantic).

Web page development and status

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101003472

A web page for A-DBO (<https://arcticpassion.eu/adbo/>) was established early in the project period (June 2022) as part of the Arctic PASSION project website (Figure 2). The page is of ‘blog format’ and such a page does not allow the full functionality of a full website, but this alternative was chosen as we found it crucial to connect well to the project throughout its lifetime while developing the desired format of a self-standing A-DBO website and exploring where its long-term home could be. A benefit of this type of page is that it is swiftly handled, so that news and updates easily can be published regularly directly by the dedicated A-DBO working group. Also, it will be easy to transfer to a future ‘home’ after the end of the project, where it could potentially be developed with more advanced functionality if needed.

The webpage has from the beginning hosted sections for News, Background, Upcoming events, Past activities, and Contacts and, hence, functioned as our hub of information for the establishment process, with particularly high activity prior to and after our main meetings by providing the agendas, registration forms, meeting minutes etc.

During spring 2024 a section with cruise/sampling-relevant information was added to the web page. This material encompasses our ‘living documents’ for planning and reporting, which are under constant development in parallel with the A-DBO development. Per now it holds the ‘A-DBO cruise package’ with the 2024 Cruise table, the Key Sampling Site positions, and the A-DBO metadata excel-sheet. The latter aims to function as a swift post-cruise report back to us of any A-DBO related sampling so that information can start flowing between the different actors at an early stage, before any data sets are formally published in dedicated (meta)data portals. These materials can easily be downloaded to be used offline (e.g. in the field).

Figure 2. Excerpts from the A-DBO webpage, in which “A-DBO Planning and Reporting tools” is the most recent addition.

As we still are in a developing stage, and priority is on being 'all-inclusive' rather than restrictive, the metadata sheet is currently open for a rather large set of parameters. The parameter list available to select from has been compiled based on the parameter lists of the Pacific DBO, the Synoptic Arctic Survey, and the Nansen Legacy and MOSAiC projects as well as on the work on Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) by the long-term Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) and the Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS).

For all these parameters, and particularly relevant for our geographical region, excellent protocols for the standard procedures for sampling and analysis are provided by the Nansen Legacy project (<https://arvenetternansen.com/>). Through their long-term work on Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs), GOOS and SOOS also provide comprehensive descriptions of parameters and methods. The A-DBO recommends the use of the protocols from these sources, and our web page provides the associated web links for easily obtaining this material. We also point to the above-mentioned related projects and programs, for which corresponding material may be in place but not published online in the same degree.

The webpage is cross-linked with the Pacific DBO website (<https://dbo.cbl.umces.edu/>) and is regularly shared in our presentations, email send-outs to the A-DBO contact list, as well as in social media announcements (mainly through LinkedIn). The "A-DBO cruise package" has also been dedicatedly communicated with all cruise leads (some of which were not yet A-DBO list members).

Further plans and future 'home' of the A-DBO web page

We will continue to increase the information content on the A-DBO web site in line with discussions and decisions being made in the A-DBO community, as well as with the rest of the pan-Arctic DBO network. Discussions have started on where to host the web page after the end of the Arctic PASSION project. We will likely recommend the SIOS portal for this (<https://sios-svalbard.org/>), but depending on technical and financial considerations we could instead decide to go for SAON (<https://data.arcticobserving.org/>), collectively with the other DBOs, or to one of the central A-DBO partner institutions.

